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АНАЛИЗ ОСНОВНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ

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ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE MODELS

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Аннотация

В данной статье рассмотрен вопрос о моделях корпоративного управления, как система управления определенного типа, которая представляет собой определенный состав органов управления акционерных обществ с особыми взаимосвязями, определенной подотчетностью, в которой воплощается определенный перечень полномочий и ответственности. Хотя структура управления акционерным обществом в каждой стране имеет специфические особенности, вместе с тем существует много общих черт корпоративного управления, что позволяет выделить основные модели корпоративного управления.

Abstract

This article discusses the issue of corporate governance models as a management system of a certain type, which is a certain composition of the management bodies of joint-stock companies with special relationships, a certain accountability, which embodies a certain list of powers and responsibilities. Although the management structure of a joint-stock company in each country has specific features, at the same time there are many common features of corporate governance, which makes it possible to identify the main models of corporate governance.

Ключевые слова: бизнес, корпоративное управление, стоимость, модель.

Keywords: business, corporate governance, value, model.

Introduction.

The emergence of corporate governance was largely associated with the emergence of the theory of corporate finance as a theory of agency relations, the essence of which, in short, was to formulate a solution to the problem of separation of ownership and control. The theory of agency relations, as is known, arose due to the fact that owners were not always able to manage organizations independently and were forced to delegate their management powers to hired managers (agents). As a rule, their competence included making significant decisions on the management of the organization, and they had a sufficient amount of information about the organization.

Theoretical aspects of research work.

The emergence of corporate governance was promoted by the development of stock markets and the emergence of so-called corporations, including public joint-stock companies in the XIX-XX centuries. During this period, an active process of separating ownership from corporate governance began. Previously, these functions were combined by one person, who, as a rule, was the owner, its main manager, or direct performer.

The main provisions of the theory of corporate finance were developed in the works of M. Jessing, W.

Meckling [2] and Yu.Fama [3], R. Brayley, S. Myers [4] in the process of studying the forms and methods of conflict resolution in the interests of principals and managers. These issues are also considered in the works of Russian authors: I. V. Nikitushkina [5], I. V. Kosorukova [6], T. V. Teplovaya [7], M. A. Eskindarov, M. A. Fedotova [8] and others. To resolve these types of conflicts, tools were usually used that pushed managers to act in the interests of shareholders and creditors. These could include various incentives, punishments, and restrictions.

In our opinion, only regulatory documents can resolve various types of conflicts. For example, corporate and securities market legislation play a huge role in resolving and eliminating agency conflicts.

Previously, in various countries of the world (USA, Great Britain, Germany, etc.), corporate governance was regulated by corporate legislation, but the development of corporate relations has led to the understanding that legislative acts alone are not enough to build an effective corporate governance system. It has become necessary for participants in corporate relations to voluntarily take on obligations in order to build relationships more flexibly, which would increase the level of trust on the part of investors. In this regard, corporate

governance codes appeared as a form of regulation of these relations.

It should be noted that quite a large number of Corporate Governance Codes have been adopted. Thus, more than 100 codes of various levels were prepared in 40 countries and regions [9], namely, international and national codes of organizations. Since mid-2018, the national codes of Australia, Hong Kong, Italy, Norway, Belgium and a number of others have been revised. In the UK, the Corporate Governance Code for Large Private Organizations came into force [10]. All these changes were related to ensuring more sustainable development of organizations. Back in 1992, the UN adopted the Concept of Sustainable Development, which, in addition to environmental protection and climate change, revealed the links between the organization's business model and such indicators as corporate social responsibility (hereinafter referred to as CSR), corporate governance, involvement of minority shareholders in the organization's management, disclosure of non-financial statements, etc.

The UN has repeatedly returned to the Concept of sustainable development in its activities: in 2000, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were established, which already combined three areas of activity: economic, social and environmental. In 2015, the UN adopted the concept of sustainable development, which defined 17 goals in the field of sustainable development, including corporate social responsibility, which is part of the corporate governance of the organization [11]. ESG investments (or responsible investing) and ESG funds became the projection of the Sustainable Development Goals.

For the first time, the term "corporate governance" and, directly, the problem of separating control and ownership functions in public joint-stock companies were considered in 1932 in the book "Modern Corporation and Private Property" [1, 2] by American economists A. Burley and G. Means. Their work demonstrates that such separation leads to the formation of a new social layer-professional managers.

They allow us to emphasize that currently there is no single concept of corporate governance. The definitions come down mainly to the fact that corporate governance is a system of relations between owners, management and other stakeholders, aimed at ensuring transparency of decisions, fair distribution of business results and increasing the investment attractiveness of the organization.

For the sake of justice, it should be noted that there is another point of view about the essence of the concept of "corporate governance". Its main provision boils down to the fact that the investor should be given the opportunity to manage the organization in accordance with the rights granted to him by law, and to control the actions of the organization's management. The goal of CG is to create an environment of trust, transparency and responsibility to encourage long-term relationships with investors.

We can agree with the opinion of I. Y. Belyaeva [1-3] that the CG system is understood as a set of tools and tools for using the potential of a corporation to achieve corporate governance goals.

Today, the role of corporate governance for organizations is quite large, as, for example, it affects the following areas of its activities:

- relationships between the organization's stakeholders
- (owners (shareholders), investors, management bodies, creditors, and other interested parties-stakeholders);
- efficiency of organization management [14, 15, 16];
- bankruptcy of the organization [1-7];
- the quality of products produced by the organization [1-8], etc.

Under the influence of all the above, namely, the history of the development of CG, its concepts, regulatory documents in the field of CG, methods of regulating corporate conflicts, etc., models of CG began to form, which are now an element of corporate relations of organizations in different countries of the world.

CG models began to form, first of all, in the USA at the beginning of the XX century [19] and influenced the activities of organizations, including the formation of a class of professional managers, and the authorized capital became less concentrated.

Undoubtedly, the CG system does not function in the same way in different countries.

This is reflected, among other things:

- if there is a division of functions between owners, the board of directors, and managers.
- in the distribution of shares between different groups of shareholders;
- in the level and form of payment of remuneration to managers;
- the degree of participation of stakeholders (not representing shareholders or managers) in management bodies.

Differences in the corporate governance system in different countries are influenced by a combination of several factors. These include, in our opinion, the following:

- the historical nature of relations between citizens and the state;
- prevailing types of economic behavior of the population;
- the degree of development of the stock market;
- share capital structure;
- allocation of resources between different financial institutions.
- ways to resolve conflicts.

Foreign experience of research work.

Thus, there are several models of corporate governance in the world, the main function of which is to build a system that promotes the implementation of investors' tasks and the protection of their interests.

In this paper, we will consider three main foreign models of CG:

- american (Anglo-American, Anglo-Saxon);
- german (German, continental);
- asian (Japanese).

Appendix B sets out the main criteria for analyzing the above -mentioned established corporate governance models.

We will describe the foreign models of CG in more detail. This will allow a deeper study of their features. First of all, we note that in the Anglo-American model, the state is not an important participant in corporate relations, but it is assigned a secondary role, whose participation should be limited only to establishing common rules for all market participants.

At the same time, in those countries where the American model of corporate governance dominates, there are a number of rules in the legislation prohibiting banks from engaging in investment activities, which limits the ability of financial institutions to own large blocks of shares in the organization. For example, in the United States in 1933, the Glass Steagall Act came into force, which introduced several prohibitions for banking organizations, for example, it was forbidden to have at their disposal share capital obtained through affiliated investment banks, to own more than 5% of the voting shares of any non -savings organization, or to exercise any control over an industrial organization.

In this situation, financial institutions do not have sufficient capacity to intervene in the current state of the organization. Investors who do not have such control are extremely sensitive to the availability of information and the determination of an unfavorable situation in the organization's affairs.

It should be noted that for organizations, the external attributes of effective corporate governance are extremely important: openness of information, the presence of a board of directors that defends the interests of shareholders and has a predominantly independent composition.

In general, it can be noted that in the American model of corporate governance, the satisfaction of the interests of the owners of an organization is its priority task, and the main distinguishing feature is that only shareholders have the right to influence the strategic decision - making process. Consequently, the interests of the corporation are identical to the interests of its owners, they delegate to managers and other employee's certain rights to manage the company.

The main responsibility of the board of directors, most of which is made up of independent directors, as the main body of the corporation is to protect the rights and interests of owners, as well as maximize their material well-being. That is, one of the functions of the board of directors is to achieve a high level of quality management system, which guarantees the growth of business value.

The United States is a leader in corporate governance, and its principles are widely used around the world. They are accepted in almost all countries, even those that are dominated by different models of corporate governance from the American one.

As a rule, there are six basic principles [20]: fair treatment of shareholders; methods of voting at shareholders' meetings (accounting for votes by proxy, etc.); transparency of reporting; openness of information about board members to shareholders; strategic plan-

ning; implementation of the developed codes of principles of relations with shareholders. So, the essence of the principles boils down to maximum openness, fairness, and ensuring equal conditions for access to information for all participants in society. At the same time, as practice shows, societies that adhere to the American model do not always follow the above principles.

In the German CG model, the state is an important subject of economic and corporate relations является государство [22-1]. The main thing here is not the success of an individual or organization, but ensuring the stability and successful development of the national economy as a whole.

The authorized capital is held by medium and large shareholders, who are usually legal entities, including banks. Cross-ownership of shares is widely used in organizations with the German model.

The most respectful way to resolve conflicts is to reach agreement between the participants in corporate relations.

In the Asian model, the main participant in economic and corporate relations is the state, which ensures the development and compliance with general rules, and directly affects business. Failure in business has traditionally been seen as the most serious blow to a person's reputation as a whole, often determining their entire future. The Board of Directors plays only a formal role.

Banks play an extremely important role in the activities of organizations. The vast majority of personal savings of the population is directed to bank deposits, and only a small part - to the stock market. The strategic goal of development is to increase market share, not to increase the profitability of the organization.

The main manager in an organization cannot make critical decisions without consulting the owners and managers of organizations that are members of the group ("keiretsu"), which the state and public opinion actively support and protect them from encroachments by foreign investors, so the share of foreign investors in Japanese organizations is minimal. In most Japanese organizations, the main owners of shares are insiders. They play an important role, both in individual organizations and in the economy as a whole. More than 70% of total equity in Japan is held by institutional owners. Judicial procedures are considered an extraordinary way to resolve conflicts.

In the Asian model, the principles of corporate governance are [22] the intersection of the interests of the organization and employees, a high degree of dependence of the latter on their organization; the priority of collectivism over individualism and equality between all employees; the balance of influence of the interests of owners, managers and employees; the formation of various connections between organizations and their business partners, primarily between consumers and suppliers. This model has more advantages in terms of long-term development. In each group, the motivation of prospective relationships of participants is quite strongly developed. The model is characterized by sufficient stability of external and internal factors, low risks of bankruptcy and conflicts of interest of various participants.

The first principles of CG were developed by the OECD group and the G20 [23]. It is not mandatory to adhere to them, since they are recommendations in nature, they allow countries (not only OECD members) to analyze generally accepted rules when developing their own corporate governance codes and tools.

In this regard, we present a brief comparative analysis of foreign models based on the following additional criteria:

1) Independent directors. The choice of this criterion is related to the fact that it is the board of directors that plays a huge role in the organization, especially independent directors who have nothing to do with the organization and its management, act in the interests of the organization, make objective decisions, etc.

This is clearly stated in the Corporate Governance Code (third principle). In public joint-stock companies, the absence of independent directors on the board of directors does not give it the right to trade its securities on world exchanges.

2) Share of foreign investors. Corporate governance is one of the factors that increase the investment attractiveness of an organization [24]. Therefore, it is important to understand how much capital is attracted to each organization and to the country as a whole. This indicator, in turn, characterizes the country's openness to foreign capital inflows, the confidence of foreign investors, their role in corporate governance, the level of corporate governance in the country, and the degree of information disclosure.

3) Investment period. As mentioned above (in the description of the previous parameter), CG is one of the factors that increase the investment attractiveness of an organization. Undoubtedly, the trust of investors plays an important role for it, and it depends on whether the inflow of capital to the organization and the country as a whole will be short-term or long-term.

4) Level of remuneration for managers. The fourth principle of corporate governance under the Code is related to this criterion.

This parameter also characterizes the CG model, since corporate governance ensures a fair and equitable distribution of performance results among all managers of the organization.

5) The role of hired personnel. After studying foreign models of CG, it became clear that this parameter should be considered independently. In addition, we consider it necessary to note that the international principles of CG also consider the role of various stakeholders in the organization.

6) Degree of information disclosure. The sixth principle of corporate governance (according to the Code) is related to this criterion.

Undoubtedly, the degree of information disclosure plays a role in conducting business, since the company's activities should be transparent to all stakeholders of the organization. This determines the investment orientation, i.e. the level of investor confidence, the size of the investment, etc.

Analyzes and results of research work.

The results of the analysis allow us to draw the following conclusions:

1) The main characteristics of the American model are:

- separation of ownership rights and control over the organization;
- the board of directors consists of at least 2/3 independent directors;
- the main goal of the business is to make a profit (increase the value of the business).
- priority of competitiveness;
- large share of foreign investors;
- extremely high level of remuneration for managers;
- a fairly high degree of disclosure of information about the organization.

2) The characteristic features of the German model are:

- focus on partnership and collaboration. Not only the interests of shareholders, but also those of other participants in corporate relations should be taken into account;
- banks take an active part not only in the financing of the organization, but also in the management process;
- insignificant share of foreign investors;
- average level of remuneration for managers.
- average level of information disclosure.

3) The main characteristics of the Asian model are:

- profit is not the main goal of the business.
- focus on social cohesion, partnership and cooperation, including with the state and the main bank;
- insignificant share of foreign investors;
- low level of remuneration for managers;
- low level of information disclosure.

4) The German and Asian models of corporate governance are the most similar in their characteristics.

The presented comparative analysis is based on the published studies of such authors as M. A. Shuklin, M. A. Eskindarov, I. Yu. Belyaeva, A. G. Dementiev, S. V. Orekhov, L. S. Kudini and others.

Thus, when considering the Russian corporate governance model, we will analyze 13 criteria due to the fact that generally accepted comparative criteria do not fully reveal the essence of CG models.

The choice of corporate governance model depends on the structure of the organization, its tasks in economic activity. Within one organization, one model of corporate governance most often prevails. If the model is not implemented effectively or is not available, the organization may face other significant difficulties.

The first is the loss of its position in the market in a highly competitive environment.

The second is insufficiently organized production activities.

As already noted, the problem of forming the Russian model of CG is analyzed in detail in the works of M. A. Shuklina [25], A. G. Dementieva [22-6], S. V. Orekhova and L. Sh. Kudin [27], K. A. Melikyan [28] and others. Their works describe the prerequisites for the formation and reveal the main features of the Russian corporate governance model.

In practice, corporate governance of organizations includes elements of the American, German, and Japanese models. Let's take a closer look at each parameter of corporate governance models for a more detailed analysis:

1) Country of distribution. Of course, the Uzbek CG model will be suitable mainly for Uzbek organizations, since its functioning depends on the specifics of the market, economy, and other factors.

2) Cultural and historical features. This parameter is disclosed in several aspects. High degree of state intervention. In most scientific works, the great influence of the state on business is an essential feature of the German model. In this parameter, the Uzbek CG model is similar to the German model.

As you know, a joint-stock company is a commercial organization whose authorized capital is divided into a certain number of shares that certify the owners' binding rights in relation to the company.

Therefore, if we consider joint-stock companies, the Uzbek model is similar in this parameter to the American one, where profit-making for organizations is the main goal.

Therefore, the characteristic of this parameter is similar to the American and German models.

Economic features. In our opinion, the Uzbek model is characterized by the following: Share capital structure. According to the agency theory, the ownership structure is one of the key management mechanisms that allows resolving the conflict of separation of ownership and control, which ultimately leads to an improvement in the financial condition of the company. According to the degree of concentration of ownership, the Uzbek model is similar to the German and Asian models.

That is, most often the joint-stock property of Uzbek organizations belongs to a narrow circle of shareholders - owners.

The Uzbek stock market is poorly developed and has little liquidity, which indicates the analogy of this indicator with the German model. The role of small investors is insignificant. In practice, Uzbek companies' only large Uzbek organizations' shares are traded on the Uzbek stock market, and it is not possible to attract funds from small investors.

Thus, in this parameter, the Uzbek model of corporate governance is closer to the German and Asian ones.

So, in terms of the parameter "economic features", the Uzbek model is similar to all the CG models: American, German, and Asian.

Share ownership structure. Currently, the role of minority shareholders in Uzbek organizations is insignificant, but it is expected to increase.

Most of the organizations surveyed belong to their founders. The study did not include organizations that became public or subsidiaries under divisions of large holdings.

It should be noted that the tendency to reduce the concentration of ownership is an incentive for the development of the CG system and strengthening the role of the board of directors. So, the Uzbek model in this

parameter does not correspond to any foreign model of corporate governance, which is its specific feature.

The management style in Uzbek organizations, as in German ones, is two-tiered, i.e. it consists of a board of directors and an executive body. However, despite this, the Uzbek model is more consistent with the American one due to the unclear separation of management and control functions.

Features of interaction with shareholders. In this parameter, the Uzbek model is not similar to either the Asian or German ones.

The resolution of the general meeting of shareholders may be approved without holding it (joint presence of shareholders to discuss issues on the agenda and make decisions on issues put to vote), or by absentee voting.

Degree of information disclosure. Relatively low level of information disclosure; there is non-transparency of ownership relations and information about the activities of the organization, which is not clear to investors. In our opinion, the Uzbek model CG model is similar to the German one in this parameter.

Conclusion.

So, the Uzbek CG model has elements of all three foreign models. This leads to the following conclusions:

1) Corporate governance is a system of relationships between all stakeholders of an organization.

2) Based on the consideration of the main foreign models of corporate governance (American, German and Asian), the conclusion was substantiated that each of the models of corporate governance has its own specifics, has its own strengths and weaknesses. Uzbek The German and Asian corporate governance models are similar to the Uzbek model in terms of their characteristics.

3) Generally accepted criteria for comparing CG models are not sufficient for a detailed analysis of their distinctive features: the presence of independent directors, investment orientation, and the degree of information disclosure.

4) It is rather difficult to determine the precise boundaries of each analyzed parameter, since in some cases the Uzbek CG model is simultaneously similar to several models, and most of all to the German one. However, the Uzbek corporate governance model is more similar to the German one for the following main reasons:

- high influence of the state, which contradicts the American model of CG;

- high concentration of capital in the hands of a small number of shareholders, the stock market is not very developed.

5) According to some criteria, the characteristics for Uzbek organizations do not fit any of the foreign models, which indicates the peculiarity of the development of the Uzbek CG model. These characteristics include: country of fashion distribution, share ownership structure.

At the same time, it should be taken into account that the situation with the characteristics of corporate governance criteria in Uzbekistan is not static, the legislation is changing and, accordingly, the situation in

business and its external environment, so this conclusion is an interim study that requires further clarification in the course of the changing external business environment in Uzbekistan.

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